

Radiating Charge and Changes in Internal Versus External Variables

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In classical mechanics, a body is usually described by its center-of-mass position and measurements are made from this point. Here, we call this a collective- external point, because there is no explicit appearance of internal variables associated with various molecules in the object. Even in the case of friction, it is known that the temperature of both the body and the floor increase, but these internal variables still do not appear. The focus remains on the external center-of-mass variable.

We suggest that in the case of an accelerating charged distribution, where charge distribution appears in Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, the internal variables are not removed because changes to moments, such as the dipole moment suggest a change in internal variables versus a change in r , the distance from an origin in the distribution to another point charge far away. (Note: a charged particle dipole moment qr may change through d/dt qr to qv , but this is due to constant motion. If a second derivative of d/dt yields a nonzero result, we suggest that there exist internal degrees of freedom changing within the charge distribution which are not of a collective nature.

We call r an external or collective variable. In the case of the electric potential ϕ , the electric field is: $E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial, where A is the magnetic vector potential. The $\text{grad } \phi$ piece is similar to $-\text{grad } V(x)$ in Newtonian mechanics, and if it acts on an external variable, like r , then one deals with mechanical collective features. If, however, grad acts on internal variables (which means grad becomes linked with d/dt partial), such as a d/dt change in d/dt of the dipole moment of an accelerating charge distribution, this means one no longer has a strictly collective picture, and we suggest there is non-collective energy, i.e. the radiated energy (similar to temperature in a Newtonian body undergoing friction). In other words, $-\text{grad } \phi$, no longer represents an external force due to a charge q , but there exists a piece of electric field associated strictly with internal degrees of freedom, which means that given that flux is $E \times B$ (electric field cross magnetic), there may be degrees of freedom associated with energy and momentum which are not part of the collective moving charge system. These, we suggest, are associated with radiated photons.

Newtonian Mechanics and Friction

A body consists of molecules which seem to be constrained so that the body may be described by an external variable, i.e. its center-of-mass position, but also of constraint free variables linked with temperature. In Newtonian mechanics, one seems to focus on the external center-of-mass position and does not explicitly keep variables linked with internal molecular degrees of freedom.

In particular, in the case of a body moving on a surface with friction, it is known in Newtonian mechanics that the particle slows down (a measure of its external or collective variable center-of-mass position), but one qualitatively assigns a loss in collective kinetic energy to a

heating of the body and the floor. Explicit variables for internal variables of the body and the floor do not come into play in equations.

Electromagnetism and a Constant Moving Charge Distribution

Electromagnetism seems to be based on Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, which in turn are based on experiment, as well as on Lorentz's force expression. Maxwell's equations focus on the vectors E (electric field) and magnetic field B , and these, in turn, depend on a scalar electric potential and a magnetic vector potential A through:

$$\mathbf{B} \text{ vector} = -\text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{E} \text{ vector} = -\text{grad} \phi - \frac{d}{dt} \mathbf{A} \quad ((1b))$$

Thus, charged objects or distributions of charges must obey Maxwell's equations, There is, however, an extra condition to be aware of because Maxwell's equations give rise to a continuity equation, such that:

$$\text{Energy density} = \text{constant}_1 \mathbf{E} \cdot \mathbf{E} + \text{constant}_2 \mathbf{B} \cdot \mathbf{B} \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and}$$

$$\text{Momentum density} = \text{constant}_3 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B} \quad ((2b))$$

Momentum density perpendicular to area yields the momentum leaving a surface.

If one has a charged particle or distribution at rest, there is only E , but if one views it from a frame moving at constant velocity $-v$, then there is both an E and B . Given that the system at rest is not radiating momentum, physically the system in the moving frame cannot be radiating momentum either. This means that if one has a sphere which has an area proportional to $4\pi r^2$ (r is the external variable), then E and B should each drop faster than $1/r$ (if only integer powers appear). This feature should appear from the electromagnetic equations and in fact does.

We suggest that viewing a charge distribution from a moving frame, means that each position point is associated with the same velocity (at the same time) so this is a collective feature. In other words, one has a charged entity which is not radiating momentum. The E field for the moving charge or distribution differs from the stationary E , and there is a B as well, but the system is collective (like a Newtonian body) because there are no internal degrees of freedom acting in a non-collective manner. They all have velocity v . We suggest this is like a moving Newtonian body.

The Case of an Accelerating Distribution of Charge

It is known from electromagnetism (1), that an accelerating charge distribution radiates photons. To show this, one may calculate ϕ and A explicitly, then calculate E and B and show that $E \times B$ drops the same as $1/r^2$ (the area of a sphere) for $r \rightarrow \infty$. Here, we try to argue that in the case of acceleration, collectivity of the fields is partially lost, i.e. the system is no longer only described by a changing external r , but also by a changing internal variable. This means that if ϕ were to be q/r , where q is charge, then $-\text{grad} \phi$ leads to $1/r^2$, i.e. an external variable result

due to the whole charge or charge system. If there exists internal changes in the charge distribution, then $-\text{grad}$ may act on these, leaving $1/r$ untouched. This then leads to an E which does not drop fast enough to ensure that $E \times B \rightarrow 0$ when $r \rightarrow \infty$. In other words, there is an E (and linked B) associated with momentum and energy of internal degrees of freedom (like heat in a body). The system is no longer strictly collective like a charge distribution moving at constant velocity v . We suggest that the electromagnetic case actually shows the internal (temperature like) degrees of freedom in terms which do not drop like the collective external $1/r$ variable..

In other words, an E field does not necessarily imply a charge force due to a charge distribution as it may also represent a force which is part of a photon which has no charge.

We now examine quantitatively how the internal degrees of freedom come into play in the accelerating charge distribution case, following (1).

$$\phi(r,t) = C \int_{\text{volume}} \text{charge density}(r', t-R/c) dv' / R \quad ((3))$$

Here there is an origin and a point P far away. The vector from the origin to P is: r vector. There is a piece of charge at r' vector and:

$$R = \text{magnitude} (r \text{ vector} - r' \text{ vector}) \approx r - r' \cdot r / |r| \quad ((4))$$

One sees that a retarded time is used in ((3)).

If one uses the binomial theorem on $1/R$ and a Taylor series expansion on charge density, then:

$$\phi = C/r \int \text{density} dv' + C r \cdot \int v' \text{ vector density} dv' + C (1/rr) r \cdot d/dt (\int r' \text{ vector density} dv' + \text{higher order} \quad ((5))$$

The first term of ϕ is Cq/r , where q is charge. This is the usual first order term for a charged particle with the external or collective variable r . The second term is $r \cdot \text{dipole moment} / rr$. The dipole moment represents internal variables. This is a key feature because a change in d/dt dipole moment means that an operator such as grad leaves the collective variable $1/r$ in the denominator untouched. In other words, one does not deal with a collective (external) feature, but rather with internal changes which have nothing to do with the collective charge distribution entity because they don't have the correct r drop off. The third term is $r / |r||r| \cdot d/dt$ dipole moment. In the case of constant motion, a dipole moment exists, but dp/dt does not change in time or space. It is a constant feature of the collective system. For example, the expression for E for a charge moving at a constant velocity only has terms with $1/|r||r||r|$.

A similar expression exists for A , the magnetic potential. One may see the details in (1).

$$A = C2/|r| dp/dt \text{ where } p \text{ is the dipole moment} \quad ((6))$$

For a constant velocity: $A = C3 v \phi$

Thus dp/dt simply accounts for the constant motion, i.e. qv for a charged particle, but a second derivative $d/dt dp/dt$ means something more, a change of internal degrees of freedom.

It is a feature of acceleration that d/dt or d/dr of dp/dt proportional to qv changes, suggesting internal changes not of a collective nature, i.e. associated with a collective charge distribution.

One next needs to calculate E . One may see that dA/dt partial may yield a $1/r$ term because d/dt may act on dp/dt . This does not occur in the constant velocity case because $dv/dt=0$.

In the case of $-\text{grad } \phi$, one may use $d/dr \phi \rightarrow d/dr dp/dt = 1/c d/dt d/dt p$ ((7))

Thus, there is a piece of E which goes as $1/r$ and this is not the collective external result of $1/rr$. We suggest that the power of $1/r$ is key in determining if one has a collective charge feature or degrees of freedom within the charge distribution system. The reason for this is that a nonradiating system cannot have E go as $1/r$ and B goes as $1/r$. It must have higher powers of r which means that d/dt and grad must act on the collective external variable r .

One may see that B may also go as $1/r$. An explicit result is given in (1).

The overall result is that there are pieces of E and B which drop as $1/r$ and so represent radiating momentum because they cancel rr from area. We suggest that these pieces represent E and B fields associated with noncollective degrees of freedom as they follow directly from features of changes (beyond the usual $dp/dt = qv$ one) of the dipole distribution, which measures internal degrees of freedom. Thus, in the case of acceleration, these degrees act in a way independent of collective motion, like temperature for molecules in a Newtonian body.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that Newtonian mechanics deals with external collective type variables such as the center-of-mass of a system. This means that one ignores degrees of freedom of the molecules in a body. In the case of friction, however, these degrees of freedom come into play because temperature increases. They, however, do not explicitly appear in Newtonian equations.

We try to argue that in the case of an accelerating charge distribution they do appear. If one calculates a dipole moment, then for a constant velocity one has dp/dt for a charge equaling qv , but if there is acceleration then $d/dt dp/dt$ is nonzero. We suggest this means that there is not just change due to constant motion, but to internal rearrangement or noncollective motion. In other words, internal degrees of freedom are receiving energy like in the temperature case. One may find that if these internal degrees of freedom act in noncollective ways, i.e. $d/dt dp/dt$ not zero, so that grad and d/dt partial which act on ϕ , the electric potential and A , the magnetic potential, to create E and B , actually create fields for a noncollective object. These derivatives do not act solely on the external-collective variable $1/r$. This leads to $1/r$ terms for both E and B and so $E \times B \cdot rr$ is nonzero for large r . This in turn leads to radiation being emitted.

We thus suggest that electromagnetic theory explicitl shows internal degrees of freedom acting in a non-collective manner in the case of radiation of an accelerating charge because it is

the change in the dipole moment (beyond constant v motion) which ultimately leads to the $1/r$ behaviour and photon emission.

References

1. Reitz, J. and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory. Addison-Wesley 1980. Pp 458-459